

Dehydration-Rehydration Behaviour of Kaolinite Mineral in Relation to Surface Area

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Dehydration-rehydration characteristics of kaolinite mineral are strongly influenced by various parameters and as such is an important subject of research. Weber and Roy¹ showed that thermal dehydration of kaolinite is metastable under experimental condition. Stoch² studied the significance of structural factors in dehydroxylation of kaolinite and discussed the relations between the perfections of the structures, the size of the crystal and the course of dehydroxylation through DTA and DTG curves. Mejsner³ investigated that the endothermic peak of dehydration depends on exchangeable cation. In the present investigation, dehydration-rehydration behaviour of purified kaolinite has been studied as a function of surface area at different heat treatment temperatures.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analyses (Table 1) indicate the presence of free silica in higher size fractions. Total OH content of the kaolinite lattice is very much significant and was found to be related to the surface area. The inverse relation between DTA peak temperature and surface area (Table 1) can be explained in the way that with the

increase in surface area more reaction sites become open to thermal excitation and subsequent diffusion path of the escaping water molecules shortens.

Dehydration loss and rehydration gain data of the samples are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Equilibrium dehydration curves of similar nature were exhibited by the samples (Fig. 1). The weight loss, mostly concerned with physically ad-

Fig. 1. Dehydration loss of the samples at various temperatures; sample no. (*)1, (□)2, (Δ)3, (-)4, (Δ)5 and (↑)6.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF CLAY FRACTIONS

Sample no.	SiO ₂ %	Al ₂ O ₃ %	Fe ₂ O ₃ %	LOI %	Molar ratio SiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃	CEC meq 100 g	Surface area m ² g ⁻¹	DTA Peak temp (°C)	
								Endo.	Exo.
1	48.98	38.12	0.72	12.04	2.18	5.2	3.1	600	1 080
2	48.22	38.52	0.72	12.04	2.12	6.0	5.4	590	1 040
3	47.33	39.20	0.68	12.06	2.05	8.5	8.4	590	1 070
4	47.18	39.49	0.67	12.06	2.03	9.2	9.6	590	1 050
5	46.55	39.49	0.67	12.03	2.00	12.3	12.6	590	1 030
6	46.40	39.84	0.63	12.95	1.97	15.6	19.2	560	1 020

TABLE 2—DEHYDRATION LOSS(%) OF THE SAMPLES AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Sample no.	200°	300°	400°	500°	550°	600°	700°	800°
1	0.17	0.25	0.65	6.42	8.24	10.0	10.02	10.38
2	0.18	0.42	0.76	8.44	10.33	12.56	12.59	12.81
3	0.30	0.55	0.77	11.81	12.12	13.01	13.17	13.29
4	0.31	0.63	0.82	12.49	12.87	13.19	13.54	13.73
5	0.32	0.83	0.98	12.94	13.03	13.42	13.64	13.98
6	0.44	1.55	2.70	13.50	13.91	14.76	14.95	15.18

TABLE 3—REHYDRATION GAIN(%) OF THE DEHYDRATED SAMPLES AT 100% RELATIVE HUMIDITY*

Dehydration temp.(°C)	Sample no.					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
200	0.11	0.12	0.19	0.21	0.24	0.93
300	0.12	0.16	0.18	0.25	0.35	0.99
400	0.14	0.17	0.19	0.26	0.39	1.01
500	1.10	1.79	2.46	3.48	4.85	6.03
550	1.15	1.89	2.64	3.56	4.95	6.18
600	1.55	1.98	2.84	3.82	4.98	6.22
700	1.58	1.99	2.87	3.83	5.01	6.27
800	1.60	2.11	2.93	3.87	5.10	6.57

*Data for rehydration gain at other humidity are not given.

sorbed water, was not significant upto 400°. The magnitude of adsorbed water was proportional to surface area due to the creation of a large number of broken bonds. Dehydroxylation occurred between 400 and 600° and thus a sharp inflection was observed in all cases (Fig. 1). Above 600°, dehydration loss became more or less constant. During dehydroxylation formation of metakaolin with some ordered structure occurred. Temperature region was restricted within the above mentioned region and after dehydroxylation the weight-loss curves did not overlap due to differences in the OH content that still existed.

The mathematical relationship which has been worked out between the surface area and the weight-loss at the dehydroxylation temperature (550°) was found to be

$$y = 3.2 \ln x + 4.97$$

where y is the weight-loss of the sample (g) and x the specific surface area of the sample ($\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$).

Rehydration is one of the important characteristics by which structural stability can be examined. It was studied at four different humidities.

The curves were analogous to the corresponding dehydration curves and as such one representative figure has been incorporated (Fig. 2). Maximum water adsorption occurred between 400 and 600°

Fig. 2. Rehydration gain of sample no. 4 at various relative humidities.

which might be due to the creation of non-crystalline phases during dehydroxylation. Total rehydration can be subdivided into (i) adsorption water molecules on the surface (physical adsorption) and (ii) reconstitution of OH groups in the dehydrated phases. Above 600°, rehydration gain did not show significant change which might be regarded as a stage of incubation before crystallisation. Magnitude of rehydration was found to be a positive function of surface area irrespective of temperature and humidity.

Conclusion : (i) Dehydroxylation in kaolinite lattice occurred within a specific temperature zone (400–600°) irrespective of surface area. (ii) Dehydration loss (y) followed a logarithmic relationship with the surface area (x) of the sample given as $y = 3.2 \ln x + 4.97$. (iii) Rehydration

was mostly related to disruption of lattice and as such the curves followed analogous path to dehydration. Magnitude of adsorption followed a direct relationship with surface area.

Experimental

Rajmahal (Bihar) china clay selected for the present investigation, was purified and converted to monoionic sodium form. The clay was then fractionated into six different size fractions following gravity sedimentation technique⁴. Surface area of the samples was determined in 'Carle Erba strumentazione' which was based on gas adsorption BET principle. DTA was carried out

in a Netzsch Geratabau GMBH self thermal analyser.

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